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**Buzrukov B.T.,
Narzullaeva D.U.,
Bobokha L.Yu.**

Tashkent pediatric medical institute.
e-mail: dildoranarzullaeva@yandex.ru

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF GLAUCOMA IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The review discusses diagnostic research methods and surgical methods for the treatment of glaucoma in children. Glaucoma in children is a global problem, resulting in high visual disability. Detailed examination under general anesthesia is required for diagnosis and treatment selection. The main treatment for glaucoma in children is surgical treatment. Conservative therapy plays a limited role and surgery remains the primary therapeutic method. While goniotomy or trabeculotomy ab externo are the main treatment tactics for congenital glaucoma, primary combined trabeculotomy-trabeculectomy yields good results in stabilizing intraocular pressure. Trabeculectomy with antifibrotic agents and drainage devices is effective in the treatment of refractory glaucomas.

Keywords: congenital glaucoma, goniotomy, trabeculotomy, trabeculectomy.

**Бузруков Б.Т.,
Нарзуллаева Д.У.,
Бобоха Л.Ю**

Ташкенский педиатрический медицинский институт.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ГЛАУКОМЫ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В обзоре обсуждаются диагностические методы исследования и хирургические методы лечения глаукомы у детей. Глаукома у детей является глобальной проблемой так как приводит высокой инвалидизации по зрению. Для постановки диагноза и выбора метода лечения необходимо подробное обследование под общей анестезией. Основным методом лечения глаукомы у детей является хирургическое лечение. Медикаментозная терапия играет ограниченную роль, и хирургия остается основным терапевтическим методом. В то время как гониотомия или трабекулотомия ab externo основные методы лечения врожденной глаукомы, первичная комбинированная трабекулотомия-трабекулэктомия дает хорошие результаты при стабилизации внутриглазного давления. Трабекулэктомия с антифибротическим агентом и дренажными устройствами эффективны в лечении рефрактерных глауком.

Ключевые слова: врожденная глаукома, гониотомия, трабекулотомия, трабекулэктомия.

Buzrukov B.T.,
Narzullaeva D.U.,
Boboxa L.Yu.

Toshkent pediatriya tibbiyot instituti.

BOLALARDA GLAUKOMA DIAGNOSTIKASI VA DAVOLASH XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu sharhda bolalarda glaukoma davolashning diagnostik tadqiqot usullari va jarrohlik usullarini muhokama qiladi. Bolalar glaukoma global muammodir, chunki ko'rish qobiliyatini zaifligiga olib keladi. Tashxis qo'yish va davolash usulini tanlash uchun umumiy anesteziya ostida batafsil tekshiriladi. Bolalar glaukoma davolashning asosiy usuli jarrohlikdir. Medikamentoz terapiya cheklangan. Goniomiya yoki ab externo trabekulotomiya tug'ma glaukoma davolashning asosiy usullari bo'lsa, ko'z ichi bosimini barqarorlashtirishda birlamchi kombinatsiyalangan trabekulotomiya-trabekulektomiya yaxshi natijalar beradi. Antifibrotik vosita bilan trabekulektomiya va drenaj qurilmalari refrakter glaukoma davolashda samarali bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: konjenital glaukoma, goniomiya, trabekulotomiya, trabekulektomiya.

Introduction. Congenital glaucoma is a global problem in pediatric ophthalmology. This fact poses diagnostic and therapeutic problems for pediatric ophthalmologists to improve and solve [1]. According to the World Glaucoma Association, childhood glaucoma is also classified as primary and secondary. Congenital and infantile glaucoma and juvenile open-angle glaucoma constitute primary congenital glaucoma (PCG). PCG can be further subdivided into subcategories by the age of onset. Children are prescribed PCG with infantile onset if the age of onset of glaucoma is between the period of neonatal/neonatal and late glaucoma (i.e., aged 1 to 24 months) [2]. PCG with onset at birth up to 1 month of age is referred to as primary glaucoma in newborns/neonates. Late-onset PCG is defined as a PCG with onset after 2 years.

Genetic aspect of congenital glaucoma

In most cases, congenital glaucoma is localized at the GLC3A locus on chromosome 2 (2p21). Families linked to these loci exhibit severe phenotypes with an autosomal recessive inheritance type. Some types of juvenile glaucoma with autosomal dominant inheritance were mapped on chromosome 1q23-q25 (*TIGR/MYOC* gene). [1]. Mutations in the *CYP1B1* gene (encoding the cytochrome P450 enzyme) at the GLC3A locus are associated with the PKG phenotype. It is the predominant genetic sample of PCG in the Middle East (Turkey and Saudi Arabia). It has been reported that 87% of familial and 27% of sporadic cases are associated with mutations in this gene. [3,4] Primary congenital glaucoma is associated with the following genes: *CYP1B1*, *LTBP2*, *FOXC1* (*TEK*, *ANGPT1*, *CYP1B1*, *LTBP2*, *FOXC1* (*TEK*, *ANGPT1*)). The risk of developing glaucoma in such children is 91.2%-100% of cases. Juvenile glaucoma is associated with the *MYOC* gene [5,6,7].

Diagnosis

General anaesthesia is recommended for detailed examination in the diagnosis of glaucoma in children. Most Western textbooks describe a classic triad of symptoms, including lacrimation, photophobia, and blepharospasm. Children often experience corneal edema due to corneal epithelial edema caused by intraocular pressure. Horizontal rupture lines of the Descemet's membrane (Haabs striae) are often present and may persist even after the pressure decrease. [8,9,10,11].

All types of glaucoma, including congenital ones, lead to a steady decrease in visual function. Initially, it is the peripheral vision that deteriorates, then - the central vision. In the beginning stages, vision deteriorates due to corneal edema, followed by reduction due to atrophy of the optic nerve. Visual acuity is assessed in accordance with age-standards [12,13].

It is better to perform measurements of axial length (AL) regularly as the growth of infants influences it. The growth of the eyeball can be compared with physiological growth. In glaucoma, eyeball growth is notable [14, 15,16]. Signs indicative of poor intraocular pressure control include

exceeding normal limits, a gradual increase in AL in certain reviews, and an asymmetric increase in AL in one eye compared to the other eye [17]. It is also necessary to perform a B-scan of the eyeballs and exclude any pathology of the posterior segment [5].

The basis of assessment remains the examination under anesthesia under an operating microscope. Keratometry is essential in the diagnosis and follow-up of children with glaucoma. Increasing corneal diameter is a hallmark of all forms of glaucoma in early childhood. Due to increased intraocular pressure (IOP), the corneal diameter usually increases by up to three years of age. Serial corneal diameter measurements are useful for diagnosing and monitoring glaucoma progression up to the age of 3 years. The average diameter of the cornea at birth is 10-10.5 mm horizontally, increasing by 0.5-1.0 mm in the first year of life and reaching an adult value of 11.7 mm by 7 years. A diameter >11 mm in a newborn, >12 mm in a child under 1 year of age, or > 13 mm in any age group indicates the exclusion of pediatric glaucoma.

Goldman's tonometer is the gold standard for measuring intraocular pressure. Given that the standard Goldman applanation tonometer cannot be used in children under general anesthesia in a supine position, the Perkins tonometer, a manual version of the Goldman tonometer, is preferred. IOP readings measured with other instruments should be interpreted with caution, e.g., Tono pen measurements have been shown to tend to overestimate IOP in patients with PCG with a record higher than 16 mmHg. IOP above 21 mmHg in one or both eyes are considered abnormally elevated in at least two cases. In general, the normal intraocular pressure in children is 12.02 ± 3.74 mm Hg [18]. However, when measuring IOP in neonates and infants, several factors need to be considered, such as physiological IOP in children being lower than in adults and increasing with age. General anesthesia reduces IOP by about 30%, and the measurement is stabilized only a few minutes after intubation [19]. Currently, the introduction of ricochet tonometry in the form of iCare™ (Icare Finland) has significantly improved the IOP assessment. It is a portable tonometer that does not require the use of local anesthesia and has been found to provide a reasonable estimate of IOP compared to Goldman's applanation tonometry in selected children with known or suspected glaucoma in whom IOP cannot otherwise be determined in the clinic [5]. Inspection of the fundus and evaluation of the optic disc can establish a diagnosis since the excavation of more than 0.1 cup-disc ratios in children younger than one year is abnormal [19].

Treatment of pediatric glaucoma

For many years, goniotomy remained the traditional surgery for congenital glaucoma until Burian and Smith, in 1960, simultaneously and independently described a new technique called "trabeculectomy ab externo". Redmond Smith developed what he called a "nylon thread trabeculotomy." The surgical technique of ab externo trabeculotomy was subsequently modified by Harms (1969), Dannheim (1971) and McPherson (1973). Early surgery is of paramount importance in the treatment of patients with developing glaucoma. In some regions of the world, such as the United States, patients may have only mild to moderate corneal edema when referred for treatment. These patients may be candidates for a goniotomy with a high success rate in the Western population. In other regions, such as India, and the Middle East, almost all patients have opacity and goniotomy is technically impossible. In these areas, external trabeculotomy is the first-choice procedure. When the initial trabeculotomy has a low probability of success, the trabeculotomy may be combined with trabeculectomy. Another important factor is that although most patients present with symptoms indicative of congenital glaucoma at birth or within 6 months of birth, they often manifest themselves late due to various non-medical factors. In such neglected cases, we prefer to perform ab externo combined trabeculotomy with trabeculectomy, which offers the greatest hope of success [20,21,22].

Internal access using goniotomy - originally described by Barkan. [23] In this technique, the Barkan knife is inserted through a limb at an angle of approximately between the root of the iris and the Schwalbe ring under gonioscopic view, which is then elongated by 75 degrees. A prerequisite for this procedure is a relatively clean cornea, that allows the angular structures to be clearly visualized. Success rates depend on the cornea's transparency, the disease's severity and the number of goniotomies performed. [24]

Trabeculotomy is a technique first described by Smith. [25] This is useful in cases with corneal opacity or when goniotomy procedures haven't given a positive outcome. This technique uses a conjunctival flap, followed by a half-thickness scleral flap. A scleral incision is made and a Schlemm's canal is exposed. The lower tooth of Harms trabeculotome is guided along the Schlemm's canal from the inner side, and the upper tooth visible from the outside serves as a guide. The trabeculotome is then turned towards the anterior chamber to break the inner wall of the canal. A similar procedure is repeated on the other side through the opening for 12 hours, thus opening the trabeculae for 120-180 degrees.

A new method with the use of a prolene fiber has been introduced as a new modification. This allows a 360-degree trabeculotomy and allows you to open the entire corner at once. [26] Studies have shown a 75-90% reduction in intraocular pressure after trabeculotomy. [27]

Filtration Procedures.

Trabeculectomy was first described by Cairns. [27] However, trabeculectomy procedures in PCG are not often performed due to limited success rates as a result of excessive healing response observed in children.

The use of antifibrotic agents, such as mitomycin-C and 5-fluorouracil, has shown promising results in increasing success rates. Success rates of 52 to 82% have been reported following antimetabolite-supported trabeculectomy procedures in patients with PCG [28]

Deep sclerectomy. This procedure involves lifting a partial-thickness scleral flap and removing the outer portion of the Schlemm's canal and the trabecular meshwork, including juxtacanalicular tissue, without complete penetration into the eye.

Glaucoma Drainage Devices (GDD) — The role of GDD in primary congenital glaucoma as a primary procedure is limited. GDD implantation in primary congenital glaucoma is considered in cases where primary angle procedures have proved ineffective or in advanced refractory cases. Studies have shown a 28–49% decrease in intraocular pressure one year after surgery [29].

Combined trabeculotomy and trabeculectomy.

This procedure is initiated when a previous trabeculectomy fails, or there are difficulties with catheterization of the Schlemm's canal. At the same time, trabeculotomy is added to the trabeculectomy. The tissue particles are removed from the sclera by surgical peripheral iridectomy. Caution is required when using mitomycin C.

Cyclodestructive procedures.

The procedure is intended for eyes with poor or no vision prognosis. The probability of success in these cases is about 30%. A newer modification, like a micropulse transscleral diode laser, is a better and safer alternative. [30]

It should be noted that in children, hypotensive surgery does not lead to a long-term decrease in IOP. This is not due to defects in surgery but as a result of high regenerative capacity of the tissues in children's eyes. [31]

Conclusion.

Early diagnosis and timely surgical treatment with the choice of the most optimal intervention method are the keys to success. Ophthalmologists and general practitioners should be wary of children with enlarged eyeballs or excessive lacrimation, corneal opacity, and photophobia in early childhood. It is also important to inform parents of the need to immediately contact an ophthalmologist and that delay in treatment can lead to significant concomitant eye diseases and deterioration of vision for life. If glaucoma is suspected in children, studies under anesthesia and, if necessary, surgery should be performed. Residual vision treatment as well as visual rehabilitation should be indispensable to managing children with deteriorated vision, and lifelong follow-up is mandatory.

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